

Synthesis of Substituted Oxadiazoles, Thiadiazoles and Triazoles and Evaluation of Their Biological Activity

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Manuscript received 12 November 1981, accepted 25 August 1982

Ethyl substituted anilino acetates (2a-d) have been prepared by the condensation of appropriate aniline and chloroacetic acid, followed by esterification with ethanol. The esters (2a-d) thus obtained were reacted with hydrazinehydrate (80%) to get respective carboxyhydrazides (3a-d). These on reaction with phenylisothiocyanates gave thiosemicarbazides (4a-d), which in turn formed on reaction with sodium hydroxide (4%) 4-phenyl-3-mercapto-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,2,4-triazoles (6a-d). The thiosemicarbazides on reaction with I_2 in KI and anhydrous phosphoric acid gave 2-anilino-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (5a-d) and 2-anilino-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (7a-d), respectively.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDES are convenient intermediates for the synthesis of oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles and triazoles. They are also known for their antitubercular¹, antifungal^{1,2} and hypoglycemic³ properties. 2-2'-(1',3',4'-Oxadiazolo)aminoindoles, reported from this laboratory^{4,5}, are found to possess considerable antimicrobial activity. In view of these and in continuation of our work⁶⁻⁹ in this area, the synthesis of some oxadiazole, thiadiazole and triazole derivatives are reported here.

The 4-substituted anilinoacetic acids (1a-d), prepared according to the literature methods¹⁰, were esterified¹¹ to give ethyl anilinoacetates (2a-d) in good yields. 2a showed a sharp peak at 1750 cm^{-1} in its ir spectrum indicating the presence of an ester carbonyl group. Esters (2a-d) on condensation with hydrazinehydrate (80%) in abs. alcohol gave the corresponding carboxyhydrazides (3a-d), which were allowed to react with phenylisothiocyanate to get the corresponding thiosemicarbazides (4a-d) in good yields.

The absorption peaks due to NH_2 , NH and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ were observed at 3590 , 3420 , 3410 and 1720 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of 3a-d. The broad peaks in the ir spectra of 4a at 3100 - 3350 cm^{-1} may be due to NH functions and the peaks at 1630 and 1150 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\text{C}=\text{S}$ functions.

2-Anilino-5 [4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (5a-d) were prepared by the oxidation of thiosemicarbazides (4a-d) with iodine in potassium iodide. 5a exhibited all the characteristic features in ir like NH at 3100 and 3150 cm^{-1} , absence of a peak due to the carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), and due to the conjugated $\text{C}=\text{N}$ at 1560 and 1590 cm^{-1} . This suggests that the thiosemicarbazides have undergone oxidation to give the substituted oxadiazoles (5a-d) (Table 1).

4-Phenyl-2[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-4-thiol-1,3,4-triazoles (6a-d) were obtained by refluxing

thiosemicarbazides with sodium hydroxide. Compound 6a showed the absence of NH and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ functions in its ir spectrum. Appearance of a peak due to conjugated $\text{C}=\text{N}$ at 1595 and 1605 is in conformity with the structures of 6a-d (Table 1).

2-Anilino-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (7a-d) could be obtained by the cyclodehydration of thiosemicarbazides with phosphoric acid. The ir spectrum of 7a showed peaks at 3220 and 3120 cm^{-1} , due to two NH groups. The peaks at 1540 and 1590 cm^{-1} clearly indicate the conjugated $\text{C}=\text{N}$ with the absence of $\text{C}=\text{O}$. This agrees with the structures assigned to these compounds (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-(SUBSTITUTED)ANILINOMETHYL-THIOSEMICARBAZIDES (4a-d), 4-PHENYL-3-MERCAPTO-5-[4'-(SUBSTITUTED)ANILINO]METHYL-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES (6a-d), 2-ANILINO-5-[4'-(SUBSTITUTED)-ANILINO]METHYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (5a-d) AND 2-ANILINO-5-[4'-(SUBSTITUTED)ANILINO]METHYL-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLES (7a-d)

Compound*	Yield (%)	m.p. °C	Nature	Mol. formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
4a	74	199-200	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SO	61.92 (61.15)	5.82 (5.73)	17.92 (17.83)
4b	75	123-24	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SO ₂	57.97 (58.18)	5.60 (5.45)	16.82 (16.97)
4c	80	124-25	Yellow microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SOCl	53.29 (53.89)	4.39 (4.49)	16.90 (16.77)
4d	68	164-65	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SOBr	46.97 (47.24)	3.84 (3.94)	14.57 (14.70)
5a	72	194-95	Yellow microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₄ O	69.10 (68.57)	5.63 (5.71)	19.89 (20.00)
5b	67	220-21	Yellow needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂	64.29 (64.86)	5.39 (5.41)	18.78 (18.92)
5c	78	182-83	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ OCl	60.08 (60.00)	4.32 (4.33)	18.57 (18.67)
5d	78	174-75	Brown microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ OBr	51.39 (51.87)	3.68 (3.75)	16.03 (16.14)
6a	72	277-78	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ S	63.98 (64.86)	5.38 (5.41)	18.82 (18.92)
6b	68	119-20	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SO	61.45 (61.54)	5.08 (5.13)	17.81 (17.95)
6c	76	126-27	Colourless microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SOCl	56.73 (56.96)	4.05 (4.11)	17.62 (17.72)
6d	80	290-91	Colourless needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SBr	49.42 (49.59)	3.49 (3.58)	14.95 (15.43)
7a	78	205-06	Yellow microscopic needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ S	64.72 (64.86)	5.39 (5.41)	18.78 (18.92)
7b	48	low mp	Yellow oil	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ OS	61.35 (61.54)	5.09 (5.13)	17.74 (17.95)
7c	61	161-62	Colourless needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SOCl	56.75 (56.96)	4.07 (4.11)	17.67 (17.72)
7d	55	234-35	Yellow needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SBr	49.52 (49.59)	3.48 (3.58)	15.39 (16.43)

* All the compounds were recrystallized from alcohol.

Biological activity^{12,13} :

Among the compounds tested for antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* by cup-plate method, compounds 4c and 6b showed moderate activity against *S. aureus* and compounds 3a, 4a-c, 5b, 5d, 6d and 7d showed moderate activity against *E. coli*. The remaining compounds did not show any activity against either of the organisms.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrometer in nujol, unless otherwise specified.

Condensation of aromatic amines (1a-d) : To a mixture of the aromatic amine (0.01 mole), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mole) and sodium carbonate (15 g), the required quantity of ethanol was added to make it wet. To this water (100 ml) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 3 hr. Additional quantity of sodium carbonate (5 g) was added and heating continued for another hr. The contents were cooled and extracted with ether to remove unreacted primary amine. The aq. layer was acidified with dil. acetic acid with cooling, to liberate the

condensed acid, which was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallized from ethanol.

Substituted ethyl anilinoacetates (2a-d) : Substituted anilinoacetic acid (1a-d) (0.126 mole), abs. ethanol (3 ml) and dry benzene (6 ml) were refluxed on a water bath, sulphuric acid (0.5 ml) added dropwise during refluxing and refluxing continued for ~12-14 hr. The mixture cooled and extracted with ether and the ether layer dried and distilled under reduced pressure to yield pure 2a-d.

4 (Substituted) anilinomethyl carboxyhydrazides (3a-d) : An aqueous solution of hydrazinehydrate (7 ml ; 80%) was added to a suspension of an appropriate 2a-d (0.0232 mole) in ethanol (15 ml). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 5 hr and cooled to room temperature. The hydrazides (3a-d) thus separated on cooling were filtered, washed with ethanol (2 ml), dried and crystallized from appropriate solvent.

4 (Substituted) anilinomethyl thiosemicarbazides (4a-d) : Appropriate carboxyhydrazides (3a-d) (0.002 mole) in abs. ethanol (10 ml) were dissolved by heating. To this, phenylisothiocyanate (0.04 mole) was added with stirring. This was refluxed on a water bath for 2-3 hr and cooled. The solid

separated was collected by filtration and crystallized from ethanol to get **4a-d**.

4-Phenyl-3-mercapto-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,2,4-triazoles (6a-d): Thiosemicarbazides (**4a-d**) (0.01 mole) was mixed with sodium hydroxide (4% ; 33 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux for 1 hr and treated with decolourizing charcoal. This was filtered, cooled and acidified with acetic acid carefully. The precipitate was washed with water, filtered and the compound crystallized from ethanol.

2-Anilino-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (5a-d): Thiosemicarbazides (**4a-d**) (0.01 mole) in ethanol (300 ml ; 95%) were added to NaOH (5 ml ; 4 N) with cooling and shaking. I₂ in KI (5%) was added gradually with stirring till the colour of iodine persists. The contents were refluxed on a water bath and more iodine was added if necessary. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and CS₂ and crystallized.

2-Anilino-5[4'-(substituted)anilino]methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (7a-d): Thiosemicarbazides (**4a-d**) (0.01 mole) were added with stirring to anhydrous phosphoric acid (20 ml) during 20 min. The flask was heated on an oil bath at 120° for 0.5 hr and the slurry was poured over ice-water. The solid separated was filtered and crystallized.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. G. Mehta, School of Chemistry, University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad,

for the elemental analysis and to Dr. Y. M. Jayaraj, Department of Microbiology, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga, for the antimicrobial screening. One of the authors (J.S.B.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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